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DESIGN OF THE “COPISMO”: A METHODOLOGICAL ESSAY FOR BREAK OF PARADIGM WITH A REGIONAL APPROACH

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ABSTRACT

This article presents an essay about the culture of copyist between artisans of one cooperative in the Brazilian northeast. The paper proposes an argument about the need for break standards established which limit the creativity, the innovation and the expansion of market. The term “Copismo” refers to the act to copy other pieces from another artisan. The handicraft today is a consolidated segment in the economy and should be more and more oriented for the market. Being motivated by the marketing pressures many artisans have appealed to copy pieces of others artisans that have bigger commercial exit and consequently hinder their own inventive capacity.

Keywords: Regionalism, Craft Design, Paradigm.

INTRODUCTION

We live in an age of global commercialization increasingly competitive, and often in the field of industries artisanal regional markets are not swallowed up by the opportunities for innovation. The market, according to Kotler (2000, p. 24) are “[...] global forces that continue to affect the professional and personal lives of all. ” The craft anywhere in the world brings so inseparable a mark of their cultural roots, and this, in large part, their greater value attached, because the market tends to value what’s unique and original, ethnic-inspired and with a strong reference cultural and regionalist. Although there are various features and concepts about craft, the focus of this essay covers the value-regional economic and cultural. According to Souza (1991), conceptualize the craftsmanship is quite complex because there is a debate between those

who seek to define it as a socio-economic activity and those who define it as an activity that expresses the culture of a people, region or race. Therefore, an important perspective, the craft should seek to guide their production to market expectations, while maintaining the aspects that make it a unique product, but for certain reasons it happens that the artisans symptomatically copy more than develop new craft products. Copy the product that worked in the market many times the attitude is more comfortable, safer and more economical for many artisans. The technical director, Luiz Carlos Barboza, SEBRAE draws attention to exactly this when he says: “The biggest challenge is to turn the craft into an economic activity based on best business conditions. The producer should be oriented by the market and to what extent the economic and social outcomes we all desire ”(Sebrae Crafts Magazine, 10 year anniversary edition, March 2008, n. 1, p. 8). This discussion focuses primarily on the craft potter and emphasizes specific features found in this community: the Alto do Moura (municipality of Caruaru-PE), considered by UNESCO the “Largest Center for Figurative Arts of the Americas.” This essay seeks to understand why the attitude of handmade copy is an activity so commonplace among the artisans of the Alto do Moura, and propose a discussion about breaking this cycle paradigm copismo detrimental to creativity. The challenge is to enhance the local culture due to the impact caused by the market and proposed a discussion with a focus on the rediscovery of identity values of the craftsmen to promote innovation, not mere copismo. We conducted a survey with ten craftsmen that location in order to investigate the practice of copismo, we used a questionnaire directed to

propose a discussion during the interviews about the cycle of copismo and paradigm shift.

The research developed in the Alto do Moura sought to identify four pillars in the construction of this culture of "copismo" where are present: the market, the artisans, the possibilities (of products) and buyers (users of products).

ARTISAN DESIGN - FROM THE INTUITIVE TO THE METHODOLOGICAL

According to Fajardo, limiting, Joppert (2002), the artist develops a work unusual, unique, more targeted for expression, while the craftsman can copy or shape known pieces, and it produces is more focused on the utilization. By utility we mean the decorative aspect. Initially, this distinction is necessary because the craft looks semi-industrial and aims basically a market that revolves around tourism. In artisanal production coexist in a larger scale production and small individual and community. The design plays an important role in all areas of industrialization, but their field is extended to virtually everything that is produced by companies that addresses man's relationship with its technical environment. Löbach cites as the best definition of design or posture most desirable design as a method of shaping the environment 'artificial' physical and psychological needs of people in society. And this certainly applies to the handmade process.

The craft is a means of subsistence of mankind's oldest, has an important function to employ local labor and generate income, has a strong ecological connotations of regionalism and prints the natural way. The handicrafts of the Alto do Moura is a segment of local economy whose growth has a high potential for generating employment and income, and certainly covers a semi-industrial look and a broad market focus. The design placed in this context plays an important role projetual methodological intervention, by choosing the best methodology to be applied according to the type of project, and customer needs.

The most important is not whether the craftsman or master is using the methodology of industrial designers devoted to design, but if he is solving a specific problem in the best shape and being creative. The more the designer to bring the artisan of a methodology for product development, the

better. Once the craftsman's concern is focused on their livelihood and there is some skepticism about "methodologies" because for him, create, is intuitive, mechanical - passed from father to son - and repetitive craft. Thus it is suggested that the designer approaches the craftsman naturally to a methodology that suits the most effective way to their job prospects.

Subsistence is very serious among the families of most artisans, so the existence of cooperatives and the need therefore enhances the fundraising. The craftsman, unlike the artist whose main motivation is the process of creation for its own, to produce a part is concerned with is the possibility of getting some money for their livelihood. A craftsman is primarily a producer of artifacts, and thus subject to market principles. And the market is ruthless, rejecting what does not match their expectations of consumption, like any other segment of the economy.

"The rapprochement between the craft and design, regardless of the exact formula, appears to be an inexhaustible pole for partnerships, interactive performances that underline the markets welcomed." WHITE (2003) cited in Freitas (2006, p.128).

Ally craft and design is a way to establish dialogue with the consumer market, and unite tradition and modernity. The formula for success varies depending on each case. The truth is that this mixture, when properly seasoned, results in important competitive - products with high added value, unique and better yet, in an expanding market. (Sebrae Crafts Magazine, March 2008, n. 1, p.32).

DESIGN, CRAFTSMANSHIP AND VALUE

Since 1995 the Brazilian handicraft is a government incentive program to generate job opportunities and income for the artisan, the PAB Program (Brazilian Handicraft). The program is also intended to "encourage the use of regional vocations through the preparation of the organizations and their craftspeople to the competitive market, focusing on craft production chain." Its mission is intrinsically related to the culture of innovation and paradigm shift, provided by design intervention, which is: "To establish joint actions in order to meet the challenges and leverage the many opportunities that exist for the development of the Craft Sector, generating job opportunities and income and to

encourage the use of regional vocations, leading to the preservation of local cultures and the formation of an entrepreneurial mindset, through the preparation of the organizations and their craftspeople to the competitive market. "

Considered one of the most important events of the handicrafts segment in Latin America, the FENNEART (National Fair Business of Crafts) in its 8th edition in 2008 generated a turnover of around 18 million dollars and attracted an audience of about 200 000 people at the fair. More than 600 booths, 2,500 exhibitors. (Electronic Journal SIM)

According to Paul Okamoto, CEO of the SEBRAE:

"Paradoxical as it may seem, the rampant globalization process valued the make manual. Crafts, today, is the counterpart to the massification and standardization of globalized products, while promoting the cultural revival and regional identity. "(Editorial Sebrae Crafts magazine, 10 years anniversary edition, March 2008, n. 1 , p.7).

According to research conducted at the site raised by the team of Imaginary Pernambuco, a region of rugged grown economically as dynamic so that the negative impact in some way, and "changed the region's traditional aesthetic references. An example of such a fact would be made craft production with the use of molds, which provides the production of pieces in clay figuring common objects from distant regions, like elves in gardens, among other pieces. This copismo pits and undermines the cultural identity of the community. The craftsmanship in the region is an economic necessity and a symbolic expression of the local population.

ABOUT DESIGN OF THE "COPISMO"

Also according to Fajardo et al (2002, p.17), "having gained national and international recognition, artisanal production of the Alto do Moura started to have a repetitive character and received the influences of the market it serves. The need to produce in large quantities, has led the creative activity cede space to repeat. "We must mention that in the process of interaction marketing can not prevent certain changes and interference, but not to the point of cultural relevance.

Given the above, the goal of research is to investigate and ignite a debate generated through interviews with the artisans that location. This

research was the need for qualitative data collection through interviews and photographs of the crafts displayed for sale for further analysis. After the data collected was a qualitative analysis, interviews were reviewed journals and photos.

Preliminarily concluded that it is of fundamental importance for understanding a look outside a local problem and cyclical, and that such intervention can help the artisan to reflect and understand their problems. We hope that discussion of this research will contribute to the generation of knowledge necessary to point out creative solutions in solving problems copismo in order to better market positioning of trades.

The craft is now a product inserted in the system of market economy and continually faced with direct and indirect competitors. This inevitably generates a greater orientation to market, often, unfortunately, to the detriment of cultural identity. The concern of the artisans, it is often with the production of the Issuer of its competitors. Löbach (2007, p.108) evaluates and explains that within a competitive system - in this case, industrial products - the configuration of the products does not only user needs to be conquered, but the competitor produces. And this focus on the competitor generates three modes of conduct (for the product): "1. Contempt for competitors (product differentiation), 2. Imitation of competitors' products (print product), 3. Cooperation with competitors. "

Issues and their paradigm breaks or innovation are key aspects involved in this discussion about the culture of copismo artisanal sector. The term "paradigm shift" is usually said to mean "change" or "transformation" of radical nature, something that changes the way we think and see on established standards and common. If design is seen by some as a process of solving problems, to "break the paradigm is to see new perspectives in the process of solving problems, thus creating innovation. An expert in contemporary culture of innovation, Tom Kelley (2007, p.3) emphasizes that "the development of a culture of innovation is critical to success, as important as the mapping of competitive strategies or maintaining good margins" . Market growth through innovation is the best strategy to compete, not a copy.

Was carried out by questionnaire, with one interviewee at a time, a data collection. All comments were recorded in writing. They met artisans from 16 years of age to 84. According to those interviewed all began working with modeling clay since childhood and has always taught and influenced by a close relative. It was found that the trading system under the local artisans to customize parts of the second exclusive customer requests and also copy large-scale pieces that are more commercial outlet. These are the two basic factors that govern the process of producing them.

According to the observations made on site, the dynamics of production and marketing of artisans in the Alto do Moura is to maximize the production of parts to stock and there is always that meet the commercial demand, and for that to happen there is a significant loss of creativity and quality. It was found through the testimony raised many artisans, of course, use forms, templates, to produce larger-scale parts or parts of more detailed pieces of pottery, such as the face of figurative pieces, and also make abundant use of the lathe (swivel to manufacture parts of clay) to create the base of the body of figurative pieces faster. - As a craftsman who makes use of trickery to increase the production manages to make 20 pieces per day, another line that follows a more creative and detailed produces 4 / 5 pieces on the same day.

When asked about why the culture of copismo, the results were quite homogeneous. All respondents said that the need to increase production and meet demand makes such duplication is something normal between them. But such a procedure leads drop in price and profitability, as do almost all the same artisanal product, changing a few details such as shape and color.

According to one interviewee, there are many traders, not craftsmen, who are part of a cooperative of artisans, but simply ordered parts and accessories to mount and so only apply a finish. For example, outsource part of the head and body with a craftsman with another workman, after a post-production assemble the piece. With that increase production, and immediately neutralized the original work of craftsmen. This was another aspect of copismo in Alto do Moura.

The cycle of copismo opens and moves by the market

wave, every two or three years there is a new product and a new phase of copies. There have been a season that most production was the "chickens d'Angola" (Fig. 1). Currently the most widely copied production with minor cosmetic changes are the "dolls" (Fig. 2) clay, "African", "pregnant", "valets", "maids", etc.. One of the interviewees reported that many tourists complain about the lack of a greater range of handicrafts, as if there were only "dolls" being produced, so the impression you make on a visit to Alto do Moura.

Figure 1. D'Angola Chicken in clay, from different artisans.

Figure 2. Colored clay dolls.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that the consumer market for this type of activity, especially within the state of Pernambuco, has grown, however, could be improved if there was a better understanding of this culture of consumption of products copied by craftsmen (artisans).

In particular matter in homage to the master Vitalino published in the Journal of FENNEART (Special Issue, 2002, p. 46), among other issues related to the famous craftsman, says that in the late 40's when the teacher already had a striking personal style and of

his works, "illiterate, became concerned with the record of authorship, by use of the stamp, while other craftsmen began to copy them." To date, we can say that the style and themes of Vitalino are copied. As you can see, there is a current culture of copismo to some extent beneficial, because it strengthens the regional identity, but on the other hand hinders creativity and exploring new artistic styles and expanding market more qualified.

Copy the product that worked in the market many times the attitude is more comfortable, safer and more economical because there is no development effort required to break the paradigms of mere copy.

- The craftsman must use the raw material in many ways different from traditional skills, revitalizing and redesigning parts, thereby avoiding the single copy, and also complement the use of parts made with other types of material, giving form to new things old, without interfering with local traditions.

The choice of a methodology for the craft could projectual from the point where there is a priority to leverage the market, as pointed out by Baxter (1998), whose innovation is a vital factor for the occurrence of business, where the plan covers and discovers an projectual opportunity, conduct a marketing survey, analyzing competitive products enter a new product and new opportunities.

Obviously proposing a strengthening identity and reducing the costs of what is produced.

Identified in the research craft that two stood out from other craftsmen attached to the cycle copismo exactly choose the path of differentiation. Despite the similarity of the product line craft, "dolls," both stand out for work well done intentionally and innovative in the sense of innovation and prioritization of parts for finer finishes. Obviously the production declines due to the time it takes to produce a play every hand, compensation is achieved in a market price well above the competitors that seek to lower quality and high production. Both have selected customers in Brazil and abroad. Obviously the pieces stand out at a more critical observer (see fig. 3 and 4 in the next colum).

Figure 3. Dolls worked well and labeled by craftsman

Figure 4. African dolls with excellent finish and unique details.

The example of these craftsmen is a great reference to be explored and an inventive potential of the 700 artisans who now work in their studios in Alto do Moura.

According to Kotler (1999, p. 129), "The design can clearly differentiate a product or packaging. Although a competitor could copy the design, the pioneer enjoy at least a short-term leadership. "The craftsman needs to understand that when he takes the initiative to break the paradigms of a vicious cycle of copismo he is positioning itself as a pioneer in some aspect of craft production and will take any commercial advantage over its competitors. It should be noted that a minority of artisans have experienced excellent trading results for daring to break with the culture of copismo.

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